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EDITORIAL

HermeneuticS, a Biannual Refereed International Journal, published by Youth Empowerment and Research Association (YERA), is solely devoted to provide a pragmatic forum of interaction among researchers, academicians and business executives of social studies. The journal promotes interdisciplinary research in the field of business and social sciences with a focus on recent developments, literature, culture and theory. The main aim of the publication is to give a platform to the research work done not only by professionals but new comers in the field also. IT revolution has resulted into the availability of large number of alternative journals but this journal is a major departure from the conventional literature which attempts to provide a fresh and systematic approach in comprehensive way to cover the various facets of the business and management. Overall the journal presents emerging dimensions and horizons of business and social studies in Indian as well as Global context.

We are privileged to present before you Special Issue 2017 of HermeneuticS which contains a rich blend of research paper and case studies. In this issue we have included the contributions which have thrown light on Global Opportunities For E-Commerce in India, Smart Cities Landscape and India's Stand Among Global Economies, GST and Indian Economy, Make in India- The Revolutionary Step Work Life Balance: It Organizations, Data Security Issues in E-Commerce, Impact of Demonetization on Digital Mode of Payment, Green Business – The New Front of Innovative Engagement. The articles on A Study on Financial Sector Reform Opportunities, Experiences and Challenges: An Empirical Approach are in interesting character and in future we will include the other attractive areas touched by eminent authors. We congratulate the entire team of HermeneuticS for this academic work and grateful to our Patron, Prof. S.K. Singh who has been an encouraging source and strength.

We also invite academicians, reader's community, scholars and students to come out openly with constructive and positive criticism so that improvement can be made in the coming editions.

With best wishes,

F. B. Singh
Chief Editor

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES IN CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN INDIA

Sunil Kumar*

ABSTRACT

Corporate Governance in banking sector has evolved and grown significantly as a burning issue in the last decade. Numerous Countries have issued Corporate Governance Code, and the recommendations of this code that demonstrate "Good Governance" in the corporations, banking or for any institution and undoubtedly contribute towards increased transparency, morality, ethics and disclosure. Sound and efficient corporate governance practices are the basis for inspiring the performance of companies, banking for maximizing their operational efficiency achieving sustained productivity as well as ensuring protection of Shareholder's interests. Corporate governance especially in the Co-operative sector has come into sharp focus because more and more co-operative banks in India, both in urban and rural areas and there is an ever-growing need for continuous up gradation of skills, systems, and procedures in banking institutions that are supportive of a proactive stance to prevent 'unexpected surprised'.

Introduction:

"Corporate governance is about promoting corporate fairness, transparency and accountability, trust, confidence, excellence and professionalization...It is a system by which business corporations are directed and controlled." The issue of corporate governance (CG) well had known with the publication of Jensen and Hecklings articles (1976) which emphasis a body of theoretical and empirical work on the subject. During the 1970 and 1980s, theoretical and applied research work on CG was focused primarily on US corporations. By the early 1990s similar work had been done in other developed countries such as Japan, Germany, and the United Kingdom. This was quickly followed by research on Corporate Governance in emerging markets.

The contest on corporate governance in India thus draws with the connotation deal on Anglo-American experience, literature and practice. The regulators of Indian corporate sector had been very fast to understand and apply international Corporate Governance practices based on the latest available knowledge.

Corporate Governance in Banking Sector:

The Banking sector in India also has been practice for corporate governance particularly after the introduction of financial sector reforms various expert committee on "Financial sector Reforms", Task force, constituted by Government of India under the chairman ship of Shri Jagdish Kapoor, the then Deputy Governor, RBI, Shri Balasaheb Vikhe Patil Committee on the issue of corporate governance in the cooperative credit structure. NABARD (National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development) has also asked all the state co-operative banks and District cooperative banks to constitute audit committee of the board of Directors to rationalize the account and audit of the SCB (State Co-operative Bank), and DCB (District Co-operative). According to Bimal Jalan the then Governor, RBI (Reserve Bank of India), "Corporate Governance has business of individual bank or entity, but all of us. Five

never been more important than now. It is not only the or Ten years down the lines you would not able to operate unless we have corporate governance of the best standards."

Structure of Co-operative Banks:

Co-operative banks are a group of financial institutions organized under the provisions of the co-operative societies out of the states. The main object of cooperatives banks is to provide cheap credit to their member's self-reliance and mutual co-operation are their basic principles. The structure of cooperation credit institution of India can be explained with help of chart.

Cooperative banks organization in India has three tiers set up. State co-operative bank is the apex co-operative institution in the state. District cooperative banks work of district level. At the lowest level, co-operative setup is primary credit agency which works at village level. "The working area of these banks is limited to one district only. Central co-operative banks can be divided into two parts.

1. Co-operative banking union.
2. Mixed central co-operative bank.

The membership of co-operative Banking union is given to co-operative societies only while the membership of mixed central co-operative bank can be granted to both co-operative societies and individuals. Generally all states in India are having central co-operative banks with mixed membership and are providing sufficient financial assistance to both primacy societies and individuals.

Objective of the Study:

Since corporate governance is an evolving concept, there is an ever growing need for continuous up gradation of skills, systems and procedures in making institutions that are supportive of a proactive stance to prevent unexpected surprises; No doubt, banking crises will continued to occur but corporate good governance would ensure that they are not allowed

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attain vast and overwhelming dimensions". So it shall be studied under the following points briefly. Accountability, Professionalization, Social Responsibility, Trust, Confidence, and Excellence

Hypothesis:

The frame work of the present study shall be based on the following hypothesis:

- The sign of corporate governance in the Co-operative Banks are found in traces due to which they lack professionalism.
- Cooperative Banks where the ownership of the government is dominant is accountable to public perspective and, therefore corporate Governance is not possible.
- The goals of the government in terms of cooperative banks are not compatible with purely economy incentives' therefore they do not follow the best practices as recommended by the RBI.
- Non-performing assets are those which are not been yielding income for a long period of time.

Research Methodology:

The topic of the proposed research work is contemporary but a grey area in the changing economy scenario henceforth the methodology most suitable shall be exploratory and descriptive where' an in-depth analysis of the ongoing development changes in view of different committees set up for reform of banking sector especially the cooperative banking sector shall be made to provide valuable insights in the new dimension of banking industry.

Corporate Governance issues – International best practices:

Most of the problems faced by the DCB's are due to Governance issues and connected lending. In DCB's borrowers have a significant say in the management of the banks. This has the potential of influencing the Board, to take decisions that may not always be in the interest of the depositors who constitute the most important stakeholders of a bank. Also, unlike the case of institutions the shares of which can be listed in a stock exchange and can change hands without affecting the capital, in case of DCB's the Shareholders can withdraw their contribution to capital and shrink the capital of the bank and thereby limit its ability to increase risk weighted assets and expand business.

We discussed its various aspects of the bank e.g. profitability, employee satisfaction, training aspect etc. with the bank employees and the senior management. we came across following revelations:-

- NPA level was high and was affecting the profit of the book.
- Cost of establishment was also high.
- There was adverse publicity about the functioning of bank.
- Absence of motivation to perform better.
- Poor quality of lending as well as monitoring.
- Lack of sincere efforts to increase the deposit base.

- Inadequate delegation of sanctioning powers to the Branch Managers.
- HRD issues had led to discontentment among the staff members within the organization.
- Lack of publicity about the bank's schemes particularly the deposit and advances products.
- Inadequate efforts for establishing personal contacts with potential customers.
- Need for lowering interest rates on some of the loans like CD loans and advances against NSC/KVP to remain in competition with other players in the market.
- Investment portfolio of the bank needed to be reviewed a fresh.
- Basic infrastructure facilities like drinking water, toilets, etc. are not available in many of the branches.
- Branch Managers were bogged down with routine work of the bank and hence were unable to pay adequate attention to market bank's various products and recovery of NPA loans.
- Absence of full computerization in the bank.
- Majority of the Staff were computer illiterates.

Obviously it can be easily concluded that corporate governance is a matter of serious concern in DCB India. Though these exist in system of governing the institution yet it is very inefficient and opaque.

Now let us have look at the International best practices which has been recommended by the world council of credit union.

As best practices guide, the world council governance principle for credit union which are financial cooperatives similar to our District cooperative banks. This Principle address the challenges of organizational power within credit unions at three separate levels, viz. External governance, Internal Governance and Individual Governance.

External Governance:

All financial institutions, regardless of type, one excepted to comply with the following basic standards of transparency, Auditing and financial reporting.

Transparency:

- The Board should commit to regular, honest communication of its activities with members, regulators and the general public in the spirit of full disclosure.

As for as DCB's of India is concerned and this condition is inherent all over Indian Co-operative Banks -

- There was no system of communication to the public regarding financial health of the bank of the new schemes, policies etc.
- The only method of communication to the member was dispatched annual general meeting booklet were the financial position of

the bank was mentioned, more so the AGM were held on very regular basis.

- The balance sheet as required banking regulation act was published in the newspaper run by a cooperative union which had a very limited circulation.
- The bank never published its balance sheet in the Local Newspapers. So the public in General had no clue about its financial position.
- Financial statements, compliant with generally accepted accounting principles and local regulatory standards, should be made available to members and the public.

District Cooperative bank Gorakhpur did not comply to this norm as well as it adopted an accounting system which is approved and accepted by NABARD and RBI.

- The board should ensure that the Credit union meets or exceeds the international credit union safety and soundness principles as well as any other relevant standards for financial institutions. Status of DCB had a negative network indicating that it did not meet safety standard. There was no risk management in place and NPA level is very high against the norms described by the RBI.
- The credit union should undergo annual external audits within 90 days of the end of each fiscal year. Status of DCB There was an external Audit system in place but it did not conform to the national and international best practices.
- The Audit relationship should be reexamined frequently and consideration be given to changing the auditors at least every 3-5 years in a competitive bidding process. Status of DCB , As per the recommendation of the Vaidyanathan Committee the statement of Accounts and Annual Balance Sheet are being audited by CA, but they are appointed as per instruction given by the NABARD.

Public Accounting:

The board of directors and management must be constantly cognizant of responsibilities to governmental structures, including but not limited to regulators, legislative bodies, the media, the community and the public. The Status of DCB Gorakhpur, contrary to the standard the board of directors were hardly aware of the responsibilities more over they really discussed business development plan of the bank in their board meetings, also they were least bothered about interest of stake holders of the bank.

Internal Governance:

Unlike for-profit entities, credit unions exist to serve their members. Thus, credit unions must address this additional layer of governance related to their democratic, member-driven nature. This includes a commitment to "one member, one vote", as well as

observance to the International credit union operating principles and the role of the general assembly as the highest Governing body.

Structure:

The board of directors should be composed of an odd number, no less than five and no greater than nine.

Consideration should be given to the rotation of directors. Interested general members who comply with the standards of individual governance can stand for nomination. The board should encouraged dialogue with general members at the annual general meeting.

The annual general meeting of the general assembly of members should be adequately promoted to ensure sufficient member participation.

Continuity:

The board should create strategies to maintain the competitiveness and sustainability of the credit union.

The board should create succession plans for both directors and management that ensure the continued existence of the credit union. The board should approve a disaster management and recovery plan.

Balance:

The composition of the board should aim to adequately reflect the demographic makeup of its members and balance the financial service demands of members. The board should seek to balance diversity and experience, but all directors must meet the standards of individual governance.

Accountability:

The board is formally accountable to the general assembly of members, which is the highest governing body. The role and responsibilities of the board, committees and managers should be established clearly in the bye-laws or other policies. It is the duty of the board to establish strategic direction, approve policies and monitor management's implementation of these policies and achievement of targets. It is the duty of management to prepare the plan and budget, undertake operations implement the policies approved by the board and achieve the targets set forth.

Individual Governance:

In order to perform their collective duties, the individual board members and managers have an obligation to maintain ethical conduct and professionalism and to speak with a single voice one board decision have been made. Board members are also expected to possess the skills and technical capacity necessary to fulfill their duties.

Integrity:

The Credit union should adopt a standardized code of conduct clearly explaining proper behavior. Directors or managers must not have Criminal backgrounds, recent bankruptcies or panel backgrounds. Immediate family members should not serve on the board or in

management at the same time. Board members must excuse themselves from participating in discussion and voting on matter from which they or their family have a potential conflict of interest. The board must approval loans to directors or management. All such insider loans must be made within the approved credit policy parameters and will be reported on a regular basis to the full board. Directors with delinquent loans more than three months will be removed from their position.

Competence:

All members of the board should have basic financial literacy, including the ability to interpret financial statements and standards, or commit to acquiring these skills through education or training within the first year of service. Individual members should have specialized financial or business skills and/ or a member- focused viewpoint.

Commitment:

Directors should be willing and able to commit the necessary time to the credit union. Failure to attend board meetings may result in dismissal. Director must respect the decisions of the board, adhering to all policies that have been adopted, regardless of personal opinion. The board and managers as a cohesive unit, would have to ensure the credit union's compliance with issues related to external and internal governance. In order to achieve this goal, each board member has a duty to adhere to the principles of individual governance.

Competence of Directors:

In the Context of District Cooperative Bank in India, the first issue of importance is whether there is collective expertise on the board available to meet the competitive challenges before the bank to ensure growth while maintaining soundness? In today's context, serve of the areas where expertise at the Board level is very useful is HR, IT and risk management. This enables the Board to get unbiased advice from such members on the board and managerial decisions and on matters referred to the Board. Chairman and members of the Board should ensure that the Board has a board based talent in the Board in the areas of accountancy and audit, IT, HR and other expertise and experience from industry, trade and agriculture. Domain knowledge of the Board members enormously increase the quality of governance and the chairman should be able to top of this talent to the advantage of the bank. The other aspect relating to the composition of the Board relates to 'Fit and proper' criteria for directors. Internationally, the best principles of banking regulation require that regulators who give banks licenses ensure bank are owned, controlled and managed by 'Fit and proper' Shareholders, directors and senior managers. In most countries this is done through ensuring that all significant shareholders fulfill

the fit and proper tests, all directors adhere to "Fit and proper" Criteria and appointment by the board of CEO, (Chief Executive Officer) of bank and key functionaries like CFO (Chief Finance Officers) COO (Chief Operating Officer) and auditors are approved by the regulators

Role of bank directors:

An important aspect of Corporate Governance is the role of director. It would be interesting to note that the bank for international settlement (BIS) spelt out the following principles that should guide the bank director:- understand their oversight role and their fiduciary "duty of Loyalty" and "duty of care" to bank and its shareholders; Avoid conflicts of interest, or the appearance of conflicts, in their activities with and commitment to other organizations; Rescues themselves from decisions when they have conflicts of interest that make them incapable of properly fulfilling their fiduciary duties.

Policy initiatives of Reserve Bank of India:

The various initiatives taken by Reserve Bank for stabilizing and strengthening the District Cooperative Banks. Taking a view on the crisis faced by the sector time and again, the Reserve Bank, in the annual policy for the year 2004-05, announced its decision to stop granting fresh licenses for formation of new DCB's. This was followed up with a decision not to grant any fresh branch license as well. It was made clear that this was necessitated pending a comprehensive review of the legislative and regulatory framework governing the sector. It was in this background that a decision was taken to draft a vision document for the sector to outline a framework that would facilitate the strengthening of the sector and enable to play the assigned role of providing credit to the economically weaker sections.

Technology initiatives:

In order to enhance the access to technology for DCBs Reserve Bank would consider facilitating acquisition of basic hardware and software for conducting routine operations. Further, software has also been developed to enable the DCBs to prepare and submit all returns to Reserve Bank, electronically. The software has been implemented free of cost in the banks and the officials of banks are also being provided adequate training in the using the software, which enables banks to maintain a database of return submitted of the Supervisor which is turn act as a MIS for the DCBs. The stronger DCBs also one members of Clearing house and the real time Gross settlement system.

Skills development/training, including Directors and auditors training:

To the extent that it does not lead to any conflict of interest, the Reserve Bank of India, functions also seeks to play a developmental role for the District

Cooperative banks. In this context, the order to improve the skill level of human resources and the technological infrastructure of DCB, RBI in addition to subsidized programmes also provides free of cost training on all important areas of banking operations to the staff and top management of DCBs through its own training establishments as also through off-share training programmes at regional centers that have a large network of such banks. As mentioned earlier, a software has been developed for banks to help them prepare and submit all the returns to RBI, Electronically and the software has been implemented free of cost by RBI, in the banks.

The Role and Responsibilities of Investors:

Corporate governance includes the discuss on the suitable management and control structures of a bank and the rules relating to the power relating to the power relations between owners, the board of director's management, auditors and last but not least stakeholders such as employees, suppliers, customers and the public at large. The aim of good corporate governance is to enhance the long-term value of the bank for its shareholders and all other partners. The vast significance of corporate governance is clearly apparent in this definition, which includes all stakeholders. Corporate governance integrates all the participants in a process that is both economic and social.

Competency and Training:

For all boards, helpful board governance depends on the both the competencies that individual governors fetch with them and the training that the board offered to help governors master board issues and develop the skills needed to participate effectively. Effective governance also depends on an effective selection process for new governance, which in turn rests on a clear definition of what the duties of a governor are, Duties vary depending on the type of organization involved: for profit, not for profit, government agency, and so on. However, all boards have five basic responsibilities:

- Directing and supervising strategic management and the integrated planning and implementation of the major changes needed to improve corporate performance.
- Appointing and overseeing the chief executive officer (CEO) and other officers. This includes appointing, setting terms of employment, supervising, evaluating, compensating and if necessary, removing all corporate officers, starting with the CEO. It also includes approving major organizational changes and ensuring that adequate succession plans are in place.
- Representing and reporting to the shareholders, or, in not-for-profit and governments agencies, the stakeholders.
- Protecting and enhancing the bank's assets.
- Fulfilling fiduciary and legal requirements.

Conclusion:

So, we can conclude that the Bank may take following steps to improve its recovery performance:-

- The Bank may not only fix branch-wise/PACS wise targets, but also staff-wise targets for recovery and also monitor it closely at regular interval at the CEO and Board level.
- The Bank could ensure the system of periodical visit of PACS by the designated Staff and the system of periodical scrutiny of cash book to enable it to get cash recovery deposited by the PACS instead of diverting the same.
- It may also make Endeavour for affecting co-ordination amongst the agencies deploy for recovery.
- It may also approach the State Government/District Administration for recovery of it dues under IRDP and follow of at regular intervals.
- Legal Action punctually taken against the defaulting salary earners societies and other societies.
- It should also make certain that action under section-95(A) of U.P. Co-operative Society Act- 1965, it initiate against defaulters over one year.
- The recovery drive should be under taken on a continuous basis by the Bank and not as a seasonal operation.
- The Bank may well depict specific action plan for the branches where overdue were highly intense. The recovery performance of such Branches and their affiliated societies may be reviewed periodically at the level of senior management. Henceforth below recommended committee is quite fruitful for cooperative banks of India.

The Vaidyanathan Committee:

It has, therefore, recommended the implementation of a revival package covering three broad areas and if government of India is not able to implement than its would be great loss in this sectors and dominant factors of state leaders and capitalist can be cursed the banking system ever:

Financial Assistance, Legal and Institutional Reforms and Measures to improve quality of management.

Financial Assistance:

The Cooperative Banks and PACS shall be provided financial assistance under a revival package so as to make them strong to serve the credit needs of the rural people, particularly the small and marginal farmers. Such revival package shall include assistance to wipe out accumulated losses also. The financial package shall also increase the capital base of the banks/societies and reduce the government share of equity to 25% of the total subscribed share capital of the society. Cost of training and capacity building to improve the financial management skills of the staff and board of directors is also envisaged. Financial support shall be made available for installation of uniform accounting and monitoring systems and computerization of PACS.

Legal and Institutional Reforms

- Full membership rights to all users, including depositors
- Wider access to all institutions for borrowing and investment
- Ensuring elections before end of tenure of Boards
- Exit of State equity and consequent withdrawal from Boards
- Empowering RBI to directly exercise full regulatory authority in financial matters.

Measures to improve Quality of Management

- Co-option of professionals on Boards
- Reduction of State intervention in administrative and financial affairs
- Limiting powers of State to supersede Boards
- Introduction of Prudential norms and audit by CAs.

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The field of business and social studies is dynamic and changing with an unforeseen pace, a lot of research and investigations are going on. The requirement is to spread the works done and invite valuable critics on findings. Our effort is to serve this purpose and motivate young researchers for the academic contribution. The main objective of journal is to disseminate knowledge and concept which have practical utility and meet the requirement of practicing professionals, academicians and students by focusing primarily on applied research and peer reviewed articles. The journal has been classified into following sections.

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Last date for the submission of the manuscript through mail for March Issue is 31st January and for September Issue, it is 31st July. A specimen copy of journal will be given free of cost to the first author unless otherwise indicated. All correspondence relating to editorial and related matters may kindly be addressed to;

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